

Viscoelastic Effects in Polymer Coated SAW Sensors — Bane or Boon?

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Abstract

In designing SAW sensors for electronic nose applications, the polymer thicknesses are kept sufficiently low so that the sensor response is nearly linear due to dominance of mass loading effects. The viscoelastic contributions make the response nonlinear at higher thicknesses. In this paper, we analyzed the dependence of vapor discrimination ability of SAW sensor transients on polymer thickness spanning across all regions of the sensor response – from the linear in thin film region to nonlinear in viscoelastic and resonance regions. The wavelet decomposition and principal component analysis are used to determine class separability in feature space. The class separability measure based on scatter matrices of principal components is used to as monitoring parameter for sensor performance. Contrary to normal expectation, we find that the vapor class separability is enhanced by more than an order of magnitude by operating the sensors in viscoelastic regions corresponding to thicker films, except near film resonances where it dramatically declines. It is demonstrated that the present analysis offers a new paradigm for designing high performance transient sensors through optimization of film thickness and polymer selection.

1. Introduction

Surface acoustic wave (SAW) chemical sensors are electrical feedback oscillators operating at radiofrequencies [1]. Their frequencies change in response to exposure of chemical species in vapor phase. This is achieved by functionalizing the surface wave propagation path in feedback SAW device by a thin polymer coating. The polymers are chosen for selective chemical sorption and desorption in reversible manner. An array of such SAW sensors in which each sensing element is coated with a different polymer provide the basis for making an electronic nose. The latter is the sensor array integrated with pattern recognition signal processor for information extraction and identity interpretation. The polymers in sensor array are selected to provide broad range of chemical selectivities analogous to olfactory receptor neurons in human nose, and signal processing operations mimic the odor recognition mechanism of the brain [1-3]. The selection of polymers is made to encode complimentary information about target chemicals in varied proportion so that sensor array generates distinguishable response patterns under exposure to various chemicals. An alternative to this approach utilizes analysis of transient signals [4-8]. The temporal evolution of sensor outputs depend not only on chemical affinities between vapor-polymer combinations, but also on their diffusion kinetics. These two together provide basis for vapor discrimination based on even a single sensor output. The signal processing of transient signals is usually done by wavelet analysis [5, 8] or regression analysis in phase space [9-13]. The measured responses in raw format do not lend enough discrimination between vapor classes, and development of advanced signal processing methods are essential for robust odor recognition.

Most pattern analysis methods such as principal component analysis, independent component analysis, linear discriminant analysis, partial least square regression or wavelet decomposition work on assumption that linearity holds between stimulant and sensor response. Any presence of nonlinearity is thought to mix or obliterate vapor identity information. Therefore, efforts are made either to linearize data based on prior knowledge of sensor behavior or eliminate cause of nonlinearity at signal generation stage. The theory of SAW sensor perturbations as developed by Martin, Frye and Senturia [14] predicts a complex response involving regions of linearity, nonlinearity and resonance. The fractional change of SAW oscillator frequency f due to polymer coating of thickness h and mass density ρ is given as

$$\frac{\Delta f}{f} = -\text{Im} \left[\sum_{i=1}^3 c_i \frac{\beta_i M_i}{\omega} \tanh(j\beta_i h) \right] \quad (1)$$

where $\beta_i = \alpha \left(\frac{\rho - E_i / v_0^2}{M_i} \right)^{1/2}$. In this relation, β_i denote wave vectors of waves radiated towards the film outer surface (y -direction, $i = 2$) from the film-substrate interface due to SAW propagation along z -axis ($i = 3$). The β_1 and β_3 represent shear waves having polarizations along x - and z -axes, and β_2 represents the longitudinal wave with particle displacement (polarization) along y -axis. The other notations are: k_0 SAW wave vector, v_0 SAW velocity, c_i normalized surface particle velocities and $\omega = 2\pi f$ angular frequency of unperturbed oscillator; $M_i = M_i' + jM_i''$ complex shear moduli for $i = 1, 3$ and bulk moduli for $i = 2$, and $E_i = E_i' + jE_i''$ complex elastic modulus of polymer material. The SAW propagation is taken along z -direction, film thickness in y -direction, and in-plane normal to propagation along x -direction corresponding to $i = 3, 2, 1$ respectively.

In designing SAW sensors for electronic nose applications, the polymer thicknesses are kept sufficiently low so that the sensor response is nearly linear due to dominance of mass loading effects. The viscoelastic contributions make the response nonlinear at higher thicknesses. In this paper, we analyzed the dependence of vapor discrimination ability of SAW sensor transients on polymer thickness spanning across all regions of the sensor response – from the linear in thin film region to nonlinear in viscoelastic and resonance regions. The wavelet decomposition and principal component analysis are used to determine class separability in feature space. The class separability measure based on scatter matrices of principal components is used to as monitoring parameter for sensor performance. Contrary to normal expectation, we find that the vapor class separability is enhanced by more than an order of magnitude by operating the sensors in viscoelastic regions corresponding to thicker films, except near film resonances where it dramatically declines. It is demonstrated that the present analysis offers a new paradigm for designing high performance transient sensors through optimization of film thickness and polymer selection.

2. Transient Signal Generation and Wavelet Analysis

The details of SAW sensor transient generation and wavelet analysis are described in [15, 16]. The aim of these studies is to analyse effects of polymer viscoelasticity on odor discrimination ability of transient sensors. The polymer thicknesses were varied to span from the acoustically thin region where mass loading effect dominates to the acoustically thick film regions crossing the film-resonance at $\varphi_1/\pi = 0.5$ where the viscoelastic effects are important [14, 20]. In some other related studies [17-19], the authors proposed a single-polymer multiple-thickness approach to sensor array design, and analysed effects of polymer viscoelasticity in combination with information fusion for enhancing performance of transient based SAW vapor recognition systems. The signal analysis is done by discrete wavelet decomposition (DWT) and principal component analysis (PCA) of wavelet approximation coefficients based on Daubechies3 (Db3) wavelet system. A measure of vapor class separability in feature space based on scatter matrices of the principal components (PCs) [21] is used for quantitative characterizing odor discrimination ability of these sensors. Different combinations of viscoelastic parameters ranging from the glassy to glassy-rubbery to rubbery conditions are analysed. A prototype case study of polyisobutylene (PIB) coated SAW oscillator sensors realized on STX-quartz substrate, and under exposure to seven volatile organic compounds (VOCs) — chloroform, chlorobenzene, o-dichlorobenzene, n-heptane, toluene, n-hexane and n-octane, at different concentrations over 10 ppm to 100 ppm is presented. In [16, 19], the partial-least-square-regression based fusion approach is also analyzed.

The transient signal is obtained by calculating variations in average polymer film density $\rho(t)$ due to vapor sorption and desorption as explained in [15, 16]. For analysis, the transient data is normalized with respect to vapor partition coefficient (K), film thickness (h) and vapor concentration (c_0) as $s(t) \leftarrow s(t)/Kc_0h$. The transient response is generated at step of 0.1 second by keeping 40 s for sorption and 80 s for desorption intervals. To simulate real practical conditions, an additive noise source with uniform probability distribution is also included in the sensors output. The Db3 wavelet decomposition is done up to 4th level to obtain the wavelet approximation coefficients $[cA_{j,l}, j=1,2,\dots]$. The data matrix for PCA is defined by these coefficients in columns with vapor samples along the rows. The equation (1) refers to SAW propagation in z -direction, film thickness in y -direction, and in-plane normal to propagation along x -direction. The STX-quartz SAW substrate parameters are: $v_0 = 3.158 \times 10^3$ cm.s⁻¹, and $c_1 = 0.013 \times 10^{-7}$, $c_2 = 1.142 \times 10^{-7}$ and $c_3 = 0.615 \times 10^{-7}$ in units of cm².s.g⁻¹. The polyisobutylene parameters are: mass density $\rho_p = 0.918$ g.cm⁻³, storage shear modulus $G_1 = 1.58 \times 10^9$ dyne.cm⁻²

², loss shear modulus $G_2 = 3.16 \times 10^8$ dyne.cm⁻², storage bulk modulus $K_1 = 1 \times 10^{10}$ dyne.cm⁻², loss bulk modulus $K_0 = 0$ dyne.cm⁻².

The vapors partition coefficients K and diffusion coefficients D of the 7 vapors in PIB over 298-325 K, and written as $(K, D \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1})$ are: chloroform (200, 260), chlorobenzene (4680, 230), o-dichlorobenzene (22500, 5.49), n-heptane (1200, 48), toluene (1000, 35), n-hexane (180, 160), n-octane (955, 38), see [15, 16] for details. Figure 1 shows a typical set of transient response curves along with the wavelet approximation coefficients. The SAW sensor is assumed to operate at 100 MHz nominal frequency.

3. Simulation of Viscoelastic Effects

The viscoelastic conditions of polymer coatings are usually described by qualitative descriptors: glassy, glassy-rubbery or rubbery. These labels actually refer to the range of values of the storage and loss moduli parameters of the polymers. The storage and loss modulus are respectively the real and imaginary parts of the complex modulus. The groupings are according to values (in dyne.cm⁻²) of shear modulus $G = G' + jG''$ as: $G' > 10^{10}$, $G'' \ll G'$ glassy; $10^8 < G' < 10^{10}$, $G'' < G'$ glassy-rubbery; and $G' < 10^8$, $G'' < G'$ or $G'' \sim G'$ rubbery. In transients calculation, the pure mass loading condition is simulated by setting $G'' = 0$. The variations in viscoelastic conditions can be introduced by choosing appropriate values for G' and G'' . The values of polyisobutylene (PIB) quoted above correspond to glassy-rubbery viscoelastic state. In this case, the influence

of viscoelastic effects can be studied by varying the film thickness. The influence of film thickness is conveniently described in terms of phase shifts of acoustic waves radiated towards outer surface of the film from the film-substrate interface due to SAW propagation, $\phi_s = \beta_s h$ in Eq. (1). It is known that for thin films such that $\phi_s \ll \pi/2$ the viscoelastic effects are negligible [14, 20]. The sensor response in this region is dominated by the mass loading perturbations. By varying the film thickness h , the values of ϕ_s/π can be changed over $[0, 1]$ to span viscoelasticity dominated regions crossing the film-resonance condition at $\phi_s/\pi = 0.5$. Figure 2 shows the PC score plots obtained by analyzing the data from three sensors having PIB film thicknesses corresponding to ϕ_s/π values shown. Figure 3 shows the variation of class separability measure J with PIB film thickness corresponding to ϕ_s/π over $[0, 1]$. Also shown in the figure is the effect of ignoring viscoelastic effects (dotted plot) which was obtained by setting $G'' = 0$ in calculations.

Figure 1. (a) Normalized transient response $s(t)$ of polyisobutylene (PIB) coated SAW sensor array under step exposure to 7 volatile organic compounds (as indicated). The film thickness is $h = 870$ nm corresponding to $\phi_s/\pi = 0.4$; (b) wavelet approximation coefficients transient data in (a) using Daubechies-3 wavelet system up to 4th level of decomposition.

Figure 2. Principal component scores of the first two highest eigenvalue components based on the discrete wavelet analysis of polyisobutylene-coated SAW sensor transients for the 7 vapors as indicated at bottom.

4. Results

The results shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 clearly show that by operating SAW sensors in film thickness regions where viscoelastic losses are significant makes positive influence on the vapor discrimination ability of the sensor. This is in contrast to the common approach of SAW sensor design and operation where viscoelastic effects are considered undesirable, and special efforts are made to avoid their influences either by proper selection of the polymer material or by keeping the film thickness and frequency of operation sufficiently low so that $\phi_3/\pi \ll 0.5$. This is evident in Fig. 3, where one can notice the convergence of the two curves at low ϕ_3 . A significant result shown in Fig. 3 is the enhancement in sensor ability with the film thickness. For film thicknesses below resonance, this enhancement is more rapid for lossless films than for lossy films. The finite viscoelastic loss however frustrates the film resonance, and the vapor class separability measure increases monotonically to saturation near $\phi_3/\pi = 1$. An interesting feature revealed in the PC plots in Fig. 2 is that by increasing the influence of viscoelasticity both intraclass compaction and interclass separation improve. Apparently, the intraclass scatter improves much more. The possible causes for these improvements perhaps lie in the nonlinear characteristics of the sensors responses under viscoelastic conditions. Further work is however needed to understand this link at signal generation level.

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